

Towards responsible publishing: a proposal from cOAlition S

This document summarises our vision for a community-based scholarly communication system fit for open science in the 21st century, where scholars can rapidly and transparently share the full range of their research outputs and participate in new quality control mechanisms and evaluation standards.

Why scholarly communication needs to change

The dominant publishing models are highly inequitable.

The sharing of research outputs is needlessly delayed.

The full potential of peer review is not realised.

The coupling of editorial gatekeeping with academic career incentives is damaging science.

Key concepts in our proposal

- 1. Authors should decide when and what to publish**
Authors are responsible for the dissemination of their findings. Third-party suppliers can help by offering and charging for services that facilitate peer review, publication and preservation. However, they should not prevent scholars from sharing their work as they choose.
- 2. The scholarly record should include the full range of research outputs**
By openly sharing preprints and the associated peer review reports, research can be captured in real time. This offers opportunities for reviewing and filtering outputs for the purposes of curation and research assessment.

Contribute to our consultation

We invite you to join us in:

- **Evaluating** the relevance of our draft vision, mission, and principles to you, the research community
- **Refining** our proposal to ensure it resonates with your needs
- **Identifying** any potential issues or unintended consequences and suggesting proactive solutions
- **Assessing** whether the current scholarly communication infrastructure can support this proposal, and, if not, identifying areas where research funders and others should focus their funding to enhance the infrastructure

Your views needed!

NOVEMBER 2023

Online feedback survey open to all individuals and organisations.

DECEMBER 2023

Eight focus groups with representatives of a range of sector organisations.

MARCH 2024

Online survey of researchers from around the world.

Learn more at coalition-s.org/towards-responsible-publishing